

**THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF BLENDED LEARNING ON THE RELATIONSHIP
BETWEEN STUDY HABITS AND SELF-EFFICACY BELIEFS AMONG
NON-MATHEMATICS MAJOR STUDENTS**

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The Mediating Effect of Blended Learning on the Relationship between Study Habits and Self-efficacy Beliefs among Non-mathematics Major Students

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the mediating effect of blended learning on the relationship between study habits and self-efficacy beliefs among second year non-mathematics major education students who are recently done with their mathematics subject Mathematics in the Modern World (MMW). The mean, descriptive correlational technique and mediation analysis were used in this quantitative non-experimental study. The data were collected from 175 second year non-mathematics major education students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology (KCAST). For the data analysis, Medgraph was employed in determining the mediating effect of blended learning on the relationship between study habits and self-efficacy beliefs. Findings reveal that the level of study habits was high, the level of blended learning was high, and the level of self-efficacy beliefs was also high. There were significant relationship among the three variables. Result also revealed that blended learning partially mediated or significantly affected the relationship between study habits and self-efficacy beliefs. Hence, this implies that the results offered valuable information that may be utilized by the institution, teachers, and students, as well as future researchers.

Keywords: *blended learning, study habits, self-efficacy beliefs, Philippines*

Introduction

The mathematics self-efficacy beliefs of students continue to be the major cause of today's society. The impact of having a poor self-efficacy beliefs on an individual life changes is greater than that having poor reading and writing skills. There are a number of concerns associated with the student's self-efficacy in mathematics that have influenced the conceptualizing of this research study. Self-efficacy beliefs denote an individual's confidence in their capabilities. High self-efficacy encompasses a pervasive belief in one's abilities, irrespective of the particular circumstances. Conversely, low self-efficacy entails a lack of confidence in oneself (Drew, 2022). Likely supported by Öztürk et al. (2019), learners who felt they could not solve arithmetic problems had poor self-beliefs in solving math problems, and students who lack of confidence in learning mathematics often experience failure or receive low grades in the subject. They may feel anxious and apprehensive when confronted with complex math problems.

In Java, Indonesia, particularly in Yogyakarta, the country is significantly facing challenges with students' beliefs in terms of solving math problems. It is known that these students lack of self-efficacy beliefs, and the ability to answer and solve problems. Their arithmetic and sequencing skills, as well as their ability to solve complex polynomial equations are still relatively low and still need to be improved. Students felt unconfident of their ability to solve math problems and considered math as a difficult subject for them. Based on the survey of 35 students, 14.28% of the students' showed a low average of self-efficacy beliefs which means most of them is lack of confidence that still need to be improved (Masitoh & Fitriyani, 2018). Furthermore, In'am and Sutrisno (2021) stated that if their self-efficacy beliefs is poor, they may lack confidence in their ability to answer the questions on the test.

In the Philippines, specifically in Baybay City, Leyte, based on the survey of 233 students, it was revealed that 17.17% of students do not have a presence of mathematics self-efficacy beliefs, which means those students are not significantly influenced by their self-confidence. Those type of students lacks the ability to overcome math-related challenges and lacks the motivation to generate solutions, hindering their effective learning and it is still needs to be improved (Casinillo, 2023). Furthermore, Schober et al. (2018) expressed that it is worth noting that if a student has a low level of self-efficacy beliefs, the student's effectiveness in learning is diminished due to a lack of motivation to complete their tasks as a student.

The self-efficacy beliefs in mathematics is socially relevant as it empowers individuals to overcome math-related challenges, fostering confidence and competence in problem solving. Promoting self-efficacy beliefs in mathematics holds significant societal benefits. Empowering individuals with confidence in their mathematical abilities enables them to confront challenges, not just in academics but also in problem-solving across various domains. There appears to be an agreement that there is a positive correlation between mathematics and students' academic performance. High mathematics self-efficacy is linked to strong performance in the subject. On the other hand, the study needs urgent research attention it is because low mathematics self-efficacy is associated with poor performance in mathematics. Their poor self-efficacy may affect their academic performance that may affect the learners academically, personally and emotionally. Therefore, this problem needs to be addressed immediately.

The research underscores a significant gap in understanding an issue in terms of self-efficacy beliefs and its relevance or intersection with the second year non-mathematics major students. Previous studies mostly focused on the topics about self-efficacy, improving math self-efficacy, impact of self-efficacy on mathematics, source of mathematics self-efficacy. The study of Zakariya (2022) entitled "Improving Students Mathematics Self-Efficacy", Liu et al. (2023) entitled "The Impact of Self-efficacy and Academic Motivation", and Ozcan and Kultur (2021) entitled "The Relationship between Sources of Mathematics Self-Efficacy and Mathematics Test Course".

This study, in fact, is different from the other study given the facts that this research study does correlate study habits and self-efficacy having the mediating role of blended learning. Moreover, the study was conducted at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology (KCAST), and this interest primarily the second-year non-mathematics major education students. These premises would be the prompt of this study. Several studies have made regarding to the problem to identify reasons and attempt to arrive at solutions. Hence, a gap in mathematical concepts is identified.

With this study, the researcher express desire to conduct a study related to this topic. This mediating study will be disseminated to the college students, parents, educators, academic institution, faculty, library, future researchers and other related authorities and related agencies aims to establish a dynamic scholarly interaction, allowing knowledge and share research-based discoveries. The goal of publicly disseminating these findings was to encourage, informed deliberation, inspire collaborative projects, and use the research in real-life situations, especially in public service and knowledge-related areas. Making this information widely available aims to spark discussions, collaboration, and the practical use of research findings.

Research Questions

This study's primary purpose is to determine the impact of self – concept, self – esteem, self – efficacy on the academic performance of the senior high school students. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. To ascertain the level of study habits of non-mathematics major students in terms of:
 - 1.1. note taking;
 - 1.2. use of library; and
 - 1.3. time allocation to study
2. To ascertain the level of blended learning of non-mathematics major students in terms of:
 - 2.1. online platform;
 - 2.2. face to face session; and
 - 2.3. assessment
3. To determine the level of self-efficacy beliefs of non-mathematics major students in terms of:
 - 3.1. mastery experience;
 - 3.2. vicarious experience;
 - 3.3. social persuasions; and
 - 3.4. physiological state

Literature Review

Study Habits

A student's study habits are like the building blocks of their academic success. They have the regular tasks that students do every day, much like reading, taking notes, leading study groups, and meeting learning objectives. Depending on how well it benefits the pupils, it is classified as either beneficial or detrimental. In addition to being essential for academic success, study habits also influence students' overall learning experiences and future aspirations (Tus et al., 2020).

Blended Learning

Blended learning, also called as hybrid learning or mixed-mode of education, it is a way teachers use different teaching methods in class. They mix traditional teaching with other ways, like using computers or videos. This helps students learn in different ways and makes learning more interesting. It's like having a mix of old and new ways of learning in one classroom. With blended learning, students can learn at their own pace and have more ways to understand and remember of what they have learned (Vasyura et al., 2020).

Self-Efficacy Beliefs

Self-efficacy convictions it speaks to a person's belief in their ability to perform the tasks necessary to result in specific performance achievements. Demotivation also describes the absence of interest, zeal, or inclination to carry out a task as a result of particular detrimental effects. The ability to learn and innovation relate in particular to skills, knowledge, competencies and abilities. In learning, a learner develops skills and knowledge that he or she is able to use effectively in changing situations (Lee & Falahat, 2019).

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative non-experimental research design, utilizing a descriptive-correlational technique and mediation analysis. Mediating variables, which are defined as behavioral, biological, psychological, or social constructs that transmit the effect of one variable to another, were examined. Mediation serves as a means for researchers to elucidate the process or mechanism by which one variable influences another (Price et al., 2014). Additionally, non-experimental research, whether quantitative or qualitative, is the predominant type of research utilized in the social sciences. Unlike experimental research, non-experimental research does not involve the manipulation of an independent variable or the random assignment of individuals to conditions or sequences. It is important to note

that categorizing these methods solely based on what they lack may not fully capture their distinct characteristics and contributions. (Reio, 2016).

Respondents

A second-year non-mathematics major education students: BEEd-Generalist, BSEd-English, and BSEd-Filipino was the respondents of the study. A total of 175 students out of 309 across education department. The students who were selected as respondents.

Instrument

The Likert scale, a common study rating tool, measured the thoughts of individuals on a topic. The scale usually included a series of statements or questions with response options to indicate respondents' agreement or disagreement. The response options ranged from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree," with numerous severity levels. Social science researchers employed the Likert scale in behavioral, educational, and health settings (Spector, 1992).

Procedure

The data collected from the questionnaires was analyzed using the following statistical methods. These tools was employed to compute the data and test the hypotheses at a significance level of alpha 0.05.

Ethical Considerations

The participants in this study were consist of second year non-mathematics major students within the research locale. In this regard, the researcher took measures to guarantee the safety, rights, and trust of the participants throughout the study, ensuring that the research was conducted with integrity and fairness in line with its intended purpose. Maintaining rigorous ethical standards is imperative for researchers when conducting studies involving human participants. In the case of this quantitative investigation, the foremost goal was to uphold the ethical integrity of the study to safeguard the well-being of the human participants involved. The researcher reflected how the research in all aspects were able to adhere to the following considerations from Denzin and Lincoln (2011) which focused on three core principles: informed consent; risk of harm, anonymity, and confidentiality; as well as conflict of interest.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings and results of the study on the mediating effect of blended learning on the relationship between study habits and self-efficacy beliefs among non-mathematics major students. The level of study habits, the level of blended learning, and the level self-efficacy beliefs; as well as the significant relationship between study habits and self-efficacy beliefs, the significant relationship between blended learning and significant relationship between study habits and blended learning; and the direct, indirect and total effect of the variables. Analyses and interpretations of data were done parallel to the research objectives.

Table 1. *Summary on the Level of Study Habits*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Description</i>
Note Taking	4.17	High
Use of Library	3.46	High
Time Allocation	3.97	High
Total	3.87	High

Table 2. *Summary on the Level of Blended Learning*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Description</i>
Online Platform	3.89	High
Face to face Session	4.43	Very High
Assessment	4.14	High
Total	4.15	High

Table 3. *Summary on the Level of Self-Efficacy Beliefs*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Description</i>
Mastery Experience	3.48	High
Vicarious Experience	3.86	High
Social Persuasions	3.73	High
Physiological State	3.63	High
Total	3.68	High

Table 4. *Significant Relationship between Study Habits and Self-Efficacy Beliefs*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>R-Value</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Decision @=0.05</i>
Study Habits	3.87	.513	<.001	
Self-Efficacy Beliefs	3.68			Ho Rejected

Table 5. *Significant Relationship between Blended Learning and Self-Efficacy Beliefs*

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Blended Learning	4.15	.518	<.001	Ho Rejected
Self-Efficacy Beliefs	3.68			

Table 17. *Significant Relationship between Study Habits and Blended Learning*

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Study Habits	3.87	.748	<.001	Ho Rejected
Blended Learning	4.15			

The data revealed that the level of study habits of non-mathematics major students has an overall total mean of 3.87, with the descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested. This implies that students a positive and commendable academic behavior within this group, indicating the potential for strong academic performance and success in the field of mathematics.

The data revealed that the level of blended learning of non-mathematics major students has an overall total mean of 4.15, with the descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested. This implies that students have a positive correlation between the students' utilization of blended learning methods and their academic experiences, potentially indicating strong adaptation technology-enhanced in learning strategies and a commitment to a well-rounded educational experience.

The data revealed that the level of self-efficacy beliefs of non-mathematics major students has an overall total mean of 3.68, with the descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested. This implies that students has a positive correlation between the students' self-efficacy beliefs and their academic confidence and performance. The high level of self-efficacy suggests that these students may approach challenges with a sense of competence and have the potential for continued success in their academic endeavors.

Conclusions

The level of study habits among non-mathematics major students is high which means that it is always manifested by the non-mathematics major students. This implies that non-mathematics major students exhibit consistently high study habits. This suggests a positive correlation between effective study practices and academic success within this group. Institutions and educators may consider leveraging and encouraging these strong study habits to enhance overall learning experiences and potentially improve academic outcomes for non-mathematics major students.

Furthermore, the level of blended learning among non-mathematics major students is high which means that it is always manifested by the non-mathematics major students. This implies that non-mathematics major students consistently engage in a high level of blended learning. This suggests a positive correlation between the adoption of blended learning approaches and the behavior of non-mathematics major students. It may indicate a successful integration of technology and traditional teaching methods, potentially enhancing the overall learning experience for non-mathematics major students. Educators and institutions could explore further leveraging and supporting this high level of blended learning to optimize educational outcomes for students in various disciplines.

Moreover, the level of self-efficacy beliefs among non-mathematics major students is high which means that it is always manifested by the non-mathematics major students. This implies that non-mathematics major students consistently demonstrate high self-efficacy beliefs. This suggests a positive correlation between strong beliefs in one's capabilities and the behavior of non-mathematics major students. High self-efficacy beliefs may contribute to increased motivation, resilience, and academic performance within this group. Educators and institutions could recognize and build upon these high levels of self-efficacy to support the overall success and well-being of non-mathematics major students in their academic endeavors.

Additionally, there is a significant relationship between study habits and self-efficacy beliefs among non-mathematics major students; there is a significant relationship between blended learning and self-efficacy beliefs; and also, there is a significant relationship between study habits and blended learning. This implies that the way students approach their studies correlates with their confidence in their abilities and their engagement in blended learning. Educators and institutions should recognize and address these interconnections to foster a holistic approach to learning, promoting effective study habits, enhancing self-efficacy, and optimizing the benefits of blended learning for non-mathematics major students.

Also, there is a significant relationship between study habits and self-efficacy beliefs. Also, results revealed that blended learning partially mediates on the relationship between study habits and self-efficacy beliefs.

The findings indicate that blended learning plays a partial mediating role in the relationship between study habits and self-efficacy beliefs. This underscores the importance of considering the influence of blended learning in understanding the link between study habits and students' confidence in their abilities. Educators and institutions could leverage this insight to design interventions that enhance both study habits and the effectiveness of blended learning approach, ultimately contributing to improved self-efficacy beliefs among students.

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